

Digital language and communication training for EU scientists

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Report: Cross-country comparative analysis of results from interviews and focus groups on digital science communication practices

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1. Introduction

Despite the widespread use of digital genres and digital forms of communication, European researchers have been found to have limited use of these tools (Birch-Becaas et al., 2023, Pérez- Llantada et al., 2022). In an increasingly digitalized world, this underutilization may prevent researchers from reaching wider audiences and hinder their efforts of research dissemination and science popularization. The DILAN project seeks to address this issue by offering training in digital and language communication. Accordingly, during the first year of the project, we conducted 60 interviews and six focus groups to investigate the practices of European STEMM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medical sciences) researchers and to determine their training needs to better inform our training program. This report presents the findings of the qualitative analysis carried out by Work Package 2 (WP2) members of interviews and focus groups' data and suggests recommendations for designing the training effectively.

2. Analytical procedures

To collect data about European STEMM researchers' digital science communication practices, we employed an analytical procedure that consisted of two steps: conducting interviews and focus groups and analyzing the data using AI-driven technology.

2.1 Conducting interviews and focus groups

Researchers from each partner institution interviewed ten male and female STEM researchers within their cultural context, totaling 60 individual interviews (roughly 30 hours of interview data). Interviews were harmonized through the use of a shared interview protocol, based on a collaboratively constructed interview guide. Likewise, one focus group per partner institution was conducted, totaling six focus groups (roughly 5 hours of interview data). These interviews and focus groups were primarily carried out in the local languages. They were then transcribed and translated using Microsoft Office 365. Final interview and focus group transcripts were reviewed manually.

The combined total length of the interview and focus group transcripts was 287,231 words: 262,757 words for the interviews, and 50,474 words for the focus groups.

2.1.1 Participant profiles

The participants in this study cover a diverse range of profiles and positions within the academic sphere. Individual interviews were conducted with 60 female and male STEM researchers, from six different European higher education institutions, in four different countries. 58% of the participants were female, and 42% were male. 63% were senior researchers, 10% were junior researchers, and 25% were PhD students. With regard to the focus groups, participants included not only researchers but also university officials. Specifically, 88.24% were researchers, 5.88% were university officials and 5.88% were PhD students.

Although researchers formed the majority in our focus groups, they showed a good knowledge of university policy due to their engagement as writers in local or university journals, or their previous administrative positions. They also shared their views from a researcher's point of view, while university officials provided insights from an institutional perspective. In some instances, as it was the case with the Spanish focus group, there was an interplay of perspectives between researchers and university officials.

Consequently, the nature and variety of participants' profiles was carefully considered when analyzing the data. The differences between interview and focus group participants are

2.2.1 Analytical procedure

We used Leximancer to identify the most frequent concepts and their related keywords in interviews and focus groups. We then retrieved all the interview and focus group excerpts that contained each of these concepts and scrutinized them for frequent contextual patterns and responses that may substantially inform our training. We also compared concept occurrences across partners to account for related cultural differences and similarities.

Figures 2 and 3 visually illustrate the distribution of concept occurrences across both interview and focus group data. As shown in Figure 2, for example, the most frequent concepts in interviews are “training”, “English”, “digital”, “dissemination”, “social media”, “audience”, “communication” and “open”. In contrast, the most recurrent concepts in focus groups are “training”, “English”, “university” and “research”, as indicated in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Distribution of concept occurrences in individual interviews

Figure 3. Distribution of concept occurrences in focus groups

3. Findings

3.1 Interview data

We examined the use and occurrences of eight concepts identified by Leximancer as frequent in individual interviews. These concepts are listed in Table 1, which shows their occurrence according to cultural context.

Table 1. Concept frequency in interviews per cultural context

	Spain	France	Norway	Romania	Total
Training	150	179	84	195	608
English	150	268	125	349	892
Digital	192	130	82	176	580
Dissemination	79	41	51	98	269
Social media	18	55	23	54	150
Audience	94	83	60	170	407

Communication	112	143	56	115	426
Open	63	44	44	77	228

Table 1 shows the frequency of keyword occurrence in each cultural context. Variations in these frequencies can be attributed to several factors, including policy-driven realities, researcher attitudes, cultural differences, researcher agenda and translating nuances. These factors will be explained in detail in section 4, Discussion.

3.2 Concept explanation for interview data

In this section, we briefly explain how each concept was discussed in the data and list the most frequent keywords associated with the concept. This analysis gives valuable insights into participants' perspectives and training needs.

3.2.1 Training

“Training” appeared among the most frequent keywords (n=608), as indicated in Table 1, reflecting the study’s focus and the participants’ training needs. Most participants expressed their desire to learn how to produce podcasts, infographics, graphical and video abstracts, and videos. They also expressed a need to adapt their message to wider audiences and to use English for outreach. Younger participants highlighted the importance of understanding social media algorithms to promote their work effectively, while a few participants showed interest in learning more about AI. However, overall enthusiasm for participating in our proposed training was limited.

Associated keywords: English, digital, audience, dissemination, videos

3.2.2 English

As Table 1 shows, “English” is the most recurrent concept (n=892), which highlights its critical role in research and science dissemination. Participants’ insights attest to a consensus among all participants on its importance for scientific publication and peer-to-peer communication, especially in such contexts as conferences, and for teaching purposes. On the other hand, English for outreach remains less developed as local languages dominate

outreach efforts in most cultural contexts. However, Norwegian researchers were found to use English for outreach more frequently due to the multilingual nature of their cultural context.

Furthermore, the frequent mention of English, particularly by Romanian researchers, points to its perceived role in enhancing academic visibility. The emphasis on the use of English reflects an institutional policy to improve research dissemination and boost professional development.

Associated keywords: dissemination, training, people, audience, communication

3.2.3 Digital

The concept of “digital” was used to describe the various forms of digital communication and digital genres (n=580, see Table 1). Participants recognized the importance and existence of different digital genres, though their interest in them varied. While some participants expressed enthusiasm for engaging with digital genres, concerns about quality and the opinion that such tasks should be handled by specialized departments prevail. Senior researchers, in particular, showed reluctance to adopt new digital forms of science dissemination due to established work habits. In contrast, other researchers shared accounts of their growing use of digital genres for teaching purposes since COVID-19. Among the preferred digital formats are podcasts, infographics, graphical and video abstracts, and videos. The accessibility and ease of producing podcasts made these digital forms particularly well-adapted for outreach. Infographics were highlighted as especially valuable in the public health sector, supported by accessible tools such as Canva.

Associated keywords: dissemination, communication, Twitter, social media, videos, infographics, blogs, graphical abstracts, podcasts

3.2.4 Dissemination

As shown in Table 1, “Dissemination” was most frequent in Spanish and Romanian transcripts (n=269), revealing discrepancies in research agendas. Spanish and Romanian interviewers showed a tendency to discuss this concept more often when interviewing participants. Variations in concept frequency in the remaining cultural contexts may be

attributed to translation choices and nuances.

Associated keywords: open, digital, audience, English, journal, Twitter, training

3.2.5 Audience

The concept of “audience” (n=407), as shown in Table 1, indicates participants' perspectives on the importance of identifying their audience in research dissemination. Most participants demonstrated awareness of their audience but expressed few concerns regarding outreach. Some researchers engaged with different types of audiences, including children, through outreach activities such as public talks and art shows. Yet, researchers in mathematics and physics indicated that outreach was challenging for them because it required a scientific background to fully understand their work. This suggests that disciplinary context is an important factor in how scientists decide whether or not to engage in outreach.

Associated keywords: English, dissemination, open, communication

3.2.6 Social media

The concept of “social media” emerged as the least recurrent keyword in the analysis (n=150, see Table 1). This finding, supported by participants' insights during interviews, indicates a lack of interest in social media platforms. Researchers who signaled disinterest in social media pointed to time constraints and a perception that communicating their scientific work on social media platforms falls outside their professional responsibilities. These participants believe that this should be handled by their respective institutions' communication departments. Additionally, their aversion to social media is influenced by personal negative experiences, particularly with platforms such as Twitter and the controversies associated with it.

On the other hand, participants who use social media for research dissemination and outreach highlight their use of LinkedIn and ResearchGate to remain informed about the latest research developments and maintain peer-to-peer communication. Further social media platforms, including Facebook and Instagram, are primarily used for outreach purposes as required by research projects. Furthermore, junior medical science researchers appear to be among the

most active users of social media, including on newer social media platforms such as TikTok, which they use to reach wider audiences.

Associated keywords: training, audience, Twitter, ResearchGate, dissemination

3.2.7 Open

“Open” (n=228), as shown in Table 1, was mostly found to co-occur in conjunction with “Access”, in discussions of dissemination policies and services dedicated to making research outputs freely available online. Our analysis shows a consensus among participants on the importance of Open Access publications, which they described as a significant tool of peer-to-peer communication and science dissemination.

Associated keywords: access, databases, publications, journals

3.3 Focus groups

As with individual interviews, we studied the occurrences of the four most frequent concepts in focus groups. Table 2 indicates the frequency of occurrence of the four most common concepts in focus groups across the four cultural contexts.

Table 2. Concept frequency in focus groups per cultural context

	Spain	France	Norway	Romania	Total
Training	20	20	15	7	62
English	24	66	18	44	152
University	57	22	2	31	112
Research	46	82	28	162	318

3.4 Concept explanation for focus groups

The four most frequent concepts in focus groups identified during automated analysis are

detailed below.

3.4.1 English

The concept of “English” gathered agreement among researchers regarding the importance of the English language, which was emphasized across partners and in various fields (n=152, see Table 2). Mastery of English was seen as a critical skill for publishing and international collaborations. Improving English proficiency is among the most pressing training needs expressed by researchers. Some researchers believe that younger generations of researchers and PhD students are more proficient in English than they are. In their opinion, this is a result of training efforts and institutional policies that encourage the use of English for research and science dissemination.

Researchers also mentioned language tools, such as automatic translators, that they use for publication purposes. They also highlighted the support systems provided by their respective institutions, such as translation and proofreading services.

Associated keywords: research, journals, international, publish, training

3.4.2 University

The concept of “university” was mostly discussed in relation to dissemination policies (n=112, see Table 2) and support services. Participants indicated that university policies often emphasize the importance of science dissemination to both specialist and non-specialist audiences. These policies target peers through scientific articles and conferences, while communication aimed at wider audiences via different science popularization tools, such as web pages and media interviews, is also encouraged. Universities support these practices through salary increases for high-publishing researchers, and by covering publication and conference fees.

However, challenges arise from administrative and budgetary restrictions and disciplinary diversities. STEMM disciplines are particularly encouraged to publish in English. In contrast, HHS fields like Information and Communication Science have different priorities, making a universal policy counterproductive.

Associated keywords: researchers, research institutes, English, policy

3.4.3 Training

The concept of “training” speaks of participants’ training needs and training perceptions (n=62), as indicated in Table 2. Communication training programs are seen as vital for younger researchers, in particular, in order to help them develop their transversal digital competencies and enhance their ability to engage with wider audiences and understand the needs of society. Participants have also expressed a strong desire for structured institutional support for science communication in English, focusing on the tools that can help them translate their works independently. They have then suggested providing instruction on how to use AI-based translation tools.

Associated keywords: program, needs, students

3.4.4 Research

As shown in Table 2, the concept of “research” is the most frequent (n=318), as it was discussed under different themes including policy and dissemination practices. Research policies at the university level are heavily influenced by local and European policies. Participants expressed the need for policies to be supportive and not merely prescriptive. According to participants, this could be achieved by considering disciplinary differences and providing appropriate training tools and programs.

Furthermore, some researchers stated that research dissemination was conditioned by financial resources: research dissemination support funded publication mainly in international journals. They also pointed to their involvement in research projects as a way to obtain funding for both research activities and research dissemination. Other researchers finance their own research dissemination when possible. This highlights budgetary restrictions as an important barrier to researchers’ research activities and science dissemination. Participants have emphasized the need for ongoing institutional financial support for their research activities and mentioned that policy changes can be very disturbing for researchers.

Associated keywords: university, institutes, communication, English

4. Discussion of the findings

Preliminary analysis of the findings points to three factors which have shaped participants' communication strategies and practices: policy-driven realities, researcher attitude, and cultural differences. Two additional factors, researcher agenda and translating nuances, may have affected the data.

4.1 Policy-driven realities

Local and European research and science dissemination policies influence many of our participants' research and communication choices and shape their practices. These policies dictate the standards and expectations for Open Access publications, digital dissemination, and outreach activities. For example, European and local policies emphasize the importance of making research publicly accessible and encourage researchers to use Open Access journals. Researchers then align their practices with these policies to comply with funding requirements and institutional guidelines. On the other hand, these policy-driven realities often create budgetary and administrative restrictions that may influence researchers' attitudes toward newer dissemination practices. This also highlights the importance of advocating supportive policies that enhance the research sphere.

4.2 Researcher attitudes

Researchers' attitudes towards digital science dissemination and digital communication tools are rather cautious and skeptical. Many researchers believe that these activities are secondary to their primary research responsibilities. Likewise, they have a negative attitude regarding social media often due to personal experiences or the perception that using these platforms will add to their already significant workload. They also express concerns regarding the quality of the digital content they may produce and their authenticity as scientists. This overall attitude is particularly present among senior researchers who have established traditional dissemination methods and are reluctant to adopt new practices.

4.3 Cultural differences

Cultural differences across the different institutional contexts also impact researchers' science

dissemination practices. For example, researchers may have varying levels of familiarity with English as the primary language of science communication. In this regard, Romanian researchers, in particular, have a strong emphasis on mastering English to improve international visibility. Moreover, the cultural and institutional norms around the use of social media can differ significantly from one context to another. For instance, Spanish researchers seem to be more inclined to use social media platforms for science dissemination. Understanding these differences is crucial to designing an effective training program that caters to diverse research communities.

4.4 Researcher agendas

The research agendas of DILAN partners may also have influenced participants' responses. Interviewers, being fully aware of the project's nature, may have over-emphasized the study's objectives, thus influencing the interviewees' responses. This influence manifested through repetitive questions, using technical terms such as dissemination, and steering interviewees into giving specific responses. This may introduce research bias and should be taken into consideration when implementing the findings of this study.

4.5 Translation nuances

The translation of the interview and focus group transcripts from the local languages into English may also have affected the data. Nuances in language and cultural context may be lost in translation. Moreover, the act of translation involves interpretative choices made by the automatic translator, sometimes introducing new ideas and concepts that were not originally present in participants' responses. For instance, the concept of "dissemination" in Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA) interviews appeared after translating the transcripts.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

This report was prepared to provide recommendations and present the findings of the qualitative analysis of the interviews and focus groups conducted so as to inform the design of our training program. Our analysis highlighted several key findings, including the most frequent concepts in interviews and focus groups, and the interpretations of participants'

insights that allowed us to better understand their training needs.

Based on these findings, we present recommendations on the following points:

- Developing a needs-driven approach
- Taking marketing considerations into account
- Targeting the audience for training
- Teaching transferable skills
- Being mindful of the effects of institutional policy on research dissemination

5.1 Developing a needs-driven approach

The training program should be need-driven, focusing on specific areas without being overly broad. It also needs to be structured into multiple modules, with every module addressing a particular communication need. This approach ensures that the training remains relevant, addressing the unique challenges faced by researchers in various fields. Focusing on researchers' needs rather than genres and tools that they might only occasionally use will allow us to speak to the researchers' specific concerns. Therefore, researchers should be given the freedom to take modules they believe are suited to their needs. A need-driven approach is then empowering as it will help researchers make informed decisions about the relevant digital genres and tools for their specific communication needs.

5.2 Taking marketing considerations into account

It is essential to make the training attractive and engaging for overworked and overloaded researchers. This need-driven approach could be the training's marketing line. Highlighting the practical benefits of this training, such as enhanced career prospects, improved research impact, time-saving techniques, and researcher independence and skill acquisition can help us attract more participants. Also, the proper marketing materials and channels should be used, ensuring clear communication about the value of the training.

5.3 Targeting the audience for training

The training should target both senior and junior researchers, as well as PhD students. It

should suggest different training modules built around different communication situations and needs and designed for different audiences. By tailoring the content of the training to these distinct groups, the training becomes more effective and engaging.

Also, the timing of the training is particularly important for PhD students who are still learning to master traditional academic skills and genres. Introducing new training in digital science communication may be overwhelming to them or might detract from their core academic development. Hence, we should adopt a balanced approach, possibly integrating digital and traditional academic genres focusing on the shared, transferable skills needed for both. This will help PhD students who take the training see the relevance of our training and apply what they learn effectively while switching from one genre to another thanks to the transferable skills they will develop, such as mastering word choice.

5.4 Teaching transferable skills

The training should focus on building transferable skills that can be applied to both academic, professional, and digital genres. These transferable skills will empower researchers to handle a variety of tasks with greater independence and efficiency. In addition to science communication, researchers have further communicative needs related to teaching responsibilities and grant applications. Transferable skills will not only support researchers' science communication but also contribute to their overall professional development.

5.5 Being mindful of the effects of institutional policy on research dissemination

While building the content of this training, we should be mindful of European and local higher education policies and the training limitations they might create. Researchers often face budgetary and administrative restrictions that may hinder their efforts to engage in digital science communication. We should consider this in order to provide realistic and practical advice. Implementing these recommendations will allow us to design an effective training program that caters to researchers from various disciplines and ranks.

5.6 Further considerations

In addition to our recommendations, we urge training designers and fellow colleagues to carefully consider the following:

- The training should be user-centered rather than educator-centered. This can be achieved by focusing on users' needs and allowing them to select modules that are relevant to these needs.
- The training should adopt a needs-based approach in addition to a genre-based approach, emphasizing the different communication situations rather than just the various digital tools and genres that researchers may or may not be brought to use.
- Technical jargon and terms typical of our fields from Applied Linguistics, such as genre, should be clearly defined when describing the content of the training.
- Disciplinary obligations and requirements for funding should be taken into consideration.

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